

DEVELOPMENT OF MUSIC TOURISM AMONG STUDENTS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928522>

Abstract: In order to develop tourism, special economic zones are being created in our republic, tourist clusters are being created, strategic partners are being attracted to the sector, tourism infrastructure and tourism industry are being developed rapidly. Also, bold steps are being taken to rationally use the tourism potential of the regions, to produce national tourist products and bring them to the world market.

Key words: Tourism, economic regions, tourist clusters, strategic partners, tourist infrastructure, tourist opportunities, national tourist products, world market.

Our country has a huge potential for tourism and recreation, more precisely, there are 8,200 objects of cultural heritage, 209 of which are located in four museum cities - Ichan Castle in Khiva, historical centers of Bukhara and Shahrisabz cities, and Samarkand city. These cultural heritage objects are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. Recently, 7 more ancient monuments of Bukhara were included in this list by UNESCO. More than 800 cultural objects in Bukhara region will be gradually restored. The parts of the Ark fortress destroyed 100 years ago will be restored. A modern equipped history museum has been established in Bukhara, and plans are being developed to turn the village of Afshona, where medical expert Abu Ali Ibn Sina grew up, into a tourism village.

In addition, a large amount of investment will be attracted for the construction of additional tourist and recreation centers in the Amirsoy and Chimyan tourist complexes of the Tashkent region, around the Chervok reservoir and "Tashkent Sea", in the mountainous areas of Ohangaron, Angren, and the creation of thousands of new jobs. measures are being taken.

At the new stage of the reforms, the President set the following strategic tasks for tourism:

- rapid development of the tourism network, improvement of the industry management system;
- simplifying the procedures for issuing visas, licenses and permits in the field of tourism;

- foreign investments, active involvement of world brands, creation of favorable conditions for doing business in this field;
- creation of new tourism directions, development of modern types of tourism, increasing their attractiveness. [1]

Today, special attention is being paid to the development of domestic tourism in our country on the basis of the “Travel around Uzbekistan” program. On the basis of this program, the number of domestic tourists is increased from 12 million and the number of foreign tourists visiting the republic to 9 million.

Also, music has a special place in human life. It performs a certain task during holidays, various ceremonies, holidays, parties and celebrations, religious and official events, public and military marches, sports training and work.

Programs and plans aimed at wide development of musical art are being implemented in our country. In order to preserve and study our classical music heritage, and pass it on to the next generation, many competitions and prestigious international music conferences are held regularly. In order to raise the spiritual world and cultural level of the perfect generation, it is important to create appropriate conditions for our youth to enjoy the classic works of national and world music culture, as well as modern music samples that match their mood and aspirations, and to further develop music education and music tourism. is enough.

There are many opinions about the effect of music on the human body. Since ancient times, doctors have been treating mental illnesses with the help of special tunes. Experts advise dieters to eat in silence. The sounds of music stimulate the appetite. Classical music encourages you to order more expensive food. While the melodies of Mozart, Schubert, and Beethoven encourage spending more, Vivaldi’s melodies reduce the feeling of hunger.

The development of the art of Uzbek singing in the 1950s and 1960s was directly related to the decision “On the state of the art of music in Uzbekistan and its further development” adopted by the government of the republic on April 8, 1951. It happened. In this decision, the issue of priority development of Russian classical and Soviet music was set, which ensured that the art of Uzbek singing gradually abandoned its traditional national types and paid special attention to modern genres. As a result, choral ensembles and groups based on various European genres appeared in the organizations and farms of the republic on the instructions of the “higher”.

Cooperation in the field of art occupies a special place in the cultural relations of Uzbekistan with foreign countries. It was reflected in events such as

tours of artists, organization of film festivals of foreign films in the republic, screening of Uzbek films in foreign countries, organization of international exhibitions.

"In the 1960s and 1970s, Uzbek theater groups and leading artists went on tour to foreign countries - Hungary, GDR, Czechoslovakia, Poland, Mongolia, Algeria, Japan, France, England, USA and other countries. In 1965-1975, more than 100 people from the theater arts of Uzbekistan traveled to 40 countries of Europe and Asia. Among them were People's Artists Mukarrama Turgunbayeva, Galiya Izmayilova, Bernara Qariyeva, Saodat Qabulova, Mukhtar Ashrafiy, Tamarakhanim and others".[3]

The folk dance ensemble "Bahor" won great applause at its concerts in India, Sweden, Hungary, Bulgaria and other countries of the five continents. He introduced the dance art of the Uzbek people to the peoples of the world. In 1978 alone, the ensemble gave concerts in 15 Italian cities, the island of Malta and 14 French cities. In 1979, the tour of these groups in the USA was successful. In 1984, the ensemble took part in a tour in 8 countries of the world - Jordan, Peru, Greece, Australia, New Zealand, the Netherlands, Portugal, Ethiopia.[4]

State vocal-instrumental ensemble "Yalla" was a great success in the performances of the most famous youth groups held in the GDR.

Although under difficult conditions, through union structures and under serious "observation", participation in cultural events in many cases introduced Uzbekistan to world civilization and universal culture and rediscovered it. It served to establish and develop cultural relations between peoples. He made a great contribution to the development of national music pedagogy through music tourism.

In the years of independence, the attitude towards the art of music changed radically. National pedagogical aspects of personality development are studied and put into practice in the field of music and music tourism. One of the main pedagogical tasks of today is to develop tolerance among future music teachers by means of giving international status, folklore art, and music festivals. The first direction of the "Five important initiatives" implemented by the head of our state is devoted to the art of music. Also, as the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, stated in his work "High spirituality is an invincible power": "The most important thing today is that the art of music is more important than other forms of art in the development of our modern generation in the spirit of high spirituality. and has a stronger effect". [5]

One of the educational tasks of music is to provide practical support for the development of tolerance in students through music tourism. At this point, it is appropriate to touch upon the concept of tolerance.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, “Tolerance - lot, tolerance - patience, toleration, tolerance, endurance, patience towards the ideas, beliefs, feelings, lifestyle and behavior of others” to be patient; It is defined as tolerance.[6]

The inclusion of music festivals in the scope of UNESCO international cultural events is an assessment of its political and spiritual importance. Freedom and freedom, the freedom and prosperity of the country, the prosperous life of our people, the value of peaceful and peaceful days, goodness, refinement and friendship are celebrated in the navos from the eternal city, while the elegant melodies from Samarkand are the friendship, brotherhood, solidarity, true it will undoubtedly serve to glorify human qualities, the role and importance of this ancient city in the glorious history of the development of universal culture, and to widely manifest our rich musical heritage.

The art of Bakhshi, which embodies the national identity of our people in its ancient history and language, its way of life, traditions and customs, is recognized as an integral part of the universal culture, with the selfless work and creative thinking of our famous Bakhshi poets and folklorists. has been passing through centuries.

List of used literature:

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev New Development Strategy of Uzbekistan. Third edition. T: “Uzbekistan” publishing house, 2022, 440 pages
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 on "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" PQ-60
3. Tashkent v period rozvitgo sotsializma, - T.:1983, S 304-308. UzR. MDA, fund 2487, list 3, volume 5965, sheet 15
5. Karimov I.A. “High spirituality is an invincible power” - T.: “Spirituality” 2008, p. 176.
6. An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. About 80,000 words and phrases. J. IV Format - Thank you/ Editor-in-chief A. Madvaliyev.- T.: “National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan” State Scientific Publishing House, 2020. - 608 pages..

